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The status and the radioactive background control of JUNO's Water Cherenkov Detector

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Abstract

The Jiangmen Underground Neutrino Observatory, a 20 ktonD multi-purpose low background liquid scintillator detector, was proposed primarily to determine the neutrino mass ordering. To suppress the radioactivity from surrounding rocks and tag cosmic muons, the Central Detector (CD) is submerged in a Water Cherenkov Detector (WCD), which is filled with 35 kton ultrapure water and equipped with 2400 Microchannel Plate Photomultipliers. To lower the CD accidental background, the radon concentration in the ultra-pure water should be reduced to less than 10 mBq/m³. This paper will introduce the WCD's design as well as the radon removal and online monitor system.

1 JUNO

The Jiangmen Underground Neutrino Observatory (JUNO) [1] is a 20 kton liquid scintillator detector in a laboratory at 700 m underground. An excellent energy resolution and a large fiducial volume offer exciting opportunities for addressing many important topics in neutrino and astroparticle physics. With six years of data, JUNO will determine the neutrino mass ordering at a 3-4 σ significance as well as the neutrino oscillation parameters $\sin^2\theta_{12}$, Δm_{21}^2 , and $|\Delta m_{32}^2|$ to a precision of 0.6% or better by detecting reactor antineutrinos from the Taishan and Yangjiang nuclear power plants [1]. Moreover, JUNO is also capable of observing neutrinos from other sources, including supernova burst neutrinos, diffuse supernova neutrino background, geo-neutrinos, atmospheric neutrinos, and solar neutrinos.

Figure 1: Scheme of the JUNO detector.

Fig. 1 shows the scheme of the JUNO detector. The target, 20 kton of ultra-pure LS, is contained in a spherical acrylic vessel and the acrylic vessel is supported by stainless steel structures. The light emitted by LS is watched by 17612 20-inch photomultiplier tubes (PMTs) and 25600 3-inch PMTs, which are installed on the inner surface of the stainless steel structures. The entire LS detector is submerged in a Water Cherenkov Detector (WCD). On the top of the WCD, a Top Tracker (TT) is installed to precisely measure the muon tracks.

2 The WCD and the water system

The WCD is a cylinder of 43.5 m in diameter and 44 m in height, which is filled with 35 kttons of ultrapure water. The Cherenkov light produced by muons passing through the volume is detected by 2400 20-inch MicroChannel Plate PMTs (MCP-PMTs) installed on the outer surface of the stainless steel structure. The inner surface of the water pool is covered by 5 mm thickness High-Density PolyEthylene (HDPE) to prevent the rock-emanated radon from diffusing into the water. Next to the wall of the water pool, there is a mechanical structure, called birdcage act as supporting structures. Tyvek reflective foils are used to cover the inner surface of the birdcage and the outer surface of the stainless steel structure to increase the light collection efficiency of the WCD. The electron collection efficiency of the 20-inch PMTs in the CD and the WCD is affected by the geomagnetic field, losing up to 60% detection efficiency, thus a set of 32 circular coils surrounding the detector is designed to compensate for the geomagnetic field. The pool will be covered with

a black rubber sheet that is sealed by a gas-tight zipper which has been used in the Daya Bay experiment and shows excellent sealing performances [2].

To lower the accidental background in the central detector, the radon concentration in the ultra-pure water should be reduced to less than 10 mBq/m³. [1]. While the radon concentration in tap water is about 10 Bq/m³ [3]. Furthermore, radon can be continuously emanated from the detector components inside the water pool as well as from the radium soluble in the water. The radon gas in the ultrapure water should be removed through the water system.

3 The Ultrapure water system

Figure 2: Scheme of the water system.

Fig. 2 shows the scheme of the water system, which can be divided into the above-ground system and the underground water system. The water produced by the above-ground system will be transported underground by a 1200 m stainless steel water pipe. In the ultra-pure water system, Reverse Osmosis (RO) is used to remove the dissolved ions as well as the suspended species in water, including bacteria. Total Organic Carbon (TOC) is used to remove the organic matter in the water. Electro-De Ionization (EDI) is used to separate the dissolved ions from the water. Resin is used to remove the dissolved ions. Degasser is used to remove the gas from water, including oxygen, nitrogen, radon, etc.. Micro-bubbling is used to load gas into water. The radon removal efficiency of the degassers will decrease when the gas content in water is low. The micro-bubble device is used to load high-purity nitrogen to the gas to increase the radon removal efficiency.

4 The radon and radium concentrations in water measurement systems

The left of Fig. 3 shows the scheme of the radon concentration in water measurement system. The atomizer is used to transfer the radon from water into vapor by spraying and the ratio of radon concentrations in water to vapor when equilibrium follows $0.105 + 0.405 e^{-0.0502T}$, where T is the temperature in the unit of centigrade [4]. The radon concentration in the gas is determined by an electrostatically collected radon detector with a sensitivity of 0.7 mBq/m³ for one-day measurement [5]. Since 90% of the radon daughters are positively charged [5], and the moisture in the gas will affect the collection efficiency of the detector, we have a dehumidification system

Figure 3: Left: Scheme of the radon concentration in water measurement system. Middle: Mn-fiber. Right: Extraction column.

to reduce the relative humidity of the gas to less than 3%. Based on the background measurements, the sensitivity of radon concentration in water measurement system is $\sim 1 \text{ mBq/m}^3$ for one-day measurement.

Radium, the progenitor of radon, as one of the radon sources, should be well controlled. The radium concentration in water is determined by its gaseous daughter. The first step for radium measurement is to extract radium from water, and the material used in this experiment is Mn-fiber, which is polyurethane fiber with MnO_2 attached. The pictures of Mn-fiber and the extracted column are shown in Fig. 3. The background of Mn-fiber is $\sim 20 \text{ } \mu\text{Bq/g}$. The amount of water treated by the Mn-fiber and the adsorption efficiency of radium are calibrated with a $10 \text{ Bq/L } ^{226}\text{Ra}$ solution. According to the calibration results, the radium in 10 m^3 of ultrapure water can be extracted by 5 g of Mn-fiber with an efficiency of 88%. After extraction from water, the radium activity is determined by a radon emanation system. The sensitivity of the system is $\sim 13 \text{ } \mu\text{Bq/m}^3$.

5 Summary

JUNO is a multi-purpose neutrino experiment and its main physics goal is determining the neutrino mass ordering. A water Cherenkov detector is used as passive shielding and muon veto. To lower the accidental background in the center detector, the radioactivity of the water should be well controlled. For measuring the radon (radium) concentrations in water, two setups with a sensitivity of $\sim 1 \text{ mBq/m}^3$ ($\sim 13 \text{ } \mu\text{Bq/m}^3$) have been developed.

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